

Funded by
the European Union

Project Acronym	RAISE
Project Name	Research Analysis Identifier SystEm
Project Number	101058479
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-04
Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting Authority	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date	1 October 2022
Project end date	31 January 2026
Project duration	40 months

RAISE Community

(Version 1.0, 31/03/2023)

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Deliverable Name	RAISE Community
Work Package No	WP2 Requirements Elicitation, Technical and Legal Specifications
Due Date (month)	M6
Submission Date	31/03/2023
Lead Beneficiary	AUTH
Version	1.0
Status	First Draft
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Contributor(s)	RAISE Consortium
Keywords	RAISE Community, Roadmap
Type	R – Document, report
Dissemination level	PU - Public

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Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	31/03/2023	AUTH, VICOM	First version

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Abbreviations

DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier

1 Introduction

RAISE is focused on building a community of stakeholders and cultivating new synergies and research opportunities. The community will be constantly testing, and evaluating RAISE system to provide valuable feedback and ideas for improvement. The feedback will include quantitative data on system usage, such as the time spent uploading data/code and deploying it, as well as observations from usability testing while users interact with the system.

OpenAIRE and ATHENA support community engagement and have strong collaboration with EOSC network. The community will engage in online and physical meetings, including learning workshops, social networking events, and datathons that offer stakeholders the opportunity to spread the word about RAISE and win prizes based on their contribution of datasets.

To further support the RAISE community, new partnerships and incentives will be created, such as participation in new publications, collaborations, and knowledge sharing for new data science methods. The project partners' networks include research institutes, experts, consultancies, policymakers at European, national, and international levels, international organizations, and civil society. These networks enable project partners to maintain regular communication with the project's direct beneficiaries and stakeholders, ensuring that the project's target groups are effectively engaged.

To join the RAISE community, please visit: <https://raise-science.eu>.

2 From user requirements to technical requirements

RAISE is here to learn more about user needs and respond to challenges that accompany data storing and data sharing. In sum, to improve technical features based on user feedback, RAISE will follow the steps below:

1. User requirements will be collected through the interaction with the RAISE community using methods like questionnaires, interviews, focus groups.
2. Widgets will be integrated in the system with the scope to collect direct feedback from users.
3. The user requirements will be analyzed and imported to Jira. Requirements will be prioritized based on the impact on the end-users.
4. The requirements will be then communicated to technical partners through open discussion and cross-mentioning.
5. The technical partners will prioritize the requirements from a technical perspective in terms of feasibility of implementation and distribution of work.

3 RAISE proposed timeline

The project's framework will be divided in Sprints of 6 to 4 months. During each period, the consortium will deliver outputs in line with the technical implementation. Continuous monitoring will ensure that each release is covered by any changes deemed necessary.

The RAISE proposed timeline till each conclusion in January 2026 will follow the sequence of actions as listed below:

1. **(June 2023) Focus on data upload and dataset finding:** Users will be able to upload and find mock-up datasets.
2. **(September 2023) Focus on preparing the analysis script:** Users will be able to test the analysis script feature. Apart from uploading and finding mock-up datasets, they will be able to test the synthetic data generator, upload processing script and get back results.
3. **(March 2024) Focus on remotely run/processing and registering experiments:** Users will be able to run and register experiments/share algorithms publicly: they will be able to search and find dataset, experiment with synthetic dataset, and perform data versioning/code versioning.
4. **(September 2024) Focus on Get registered results & Publish Results & RAI Validates Authenticity of results:** Users will be able to upload datasets, create new versions of

datasets, and register validated results. They will be able to test the plagiarism checker, as well as register results in the RAI blockchain server. They will also be able to reuse already uploaded open algorithm.

5. **(January 2025) Popular dataset preservation:** Users will be able to identify popular datasets, as well as validate other registered results. They will also be able to test the interaction with dataset owners for popular dataset preservation.
6. **(May 2025) Enhanced processing script resources:** Users will be able to work with scripts combining more than one node datasets. They will be able to test RAISE SDKs and get results for code quality and code security. Users will be able to run consecutive experiments in multiple RAI nodes.
7. **(September 2025) Deployment of new nodes:** Users will be able to get updated results for code quality/code security. They will also be able to get RAI node status updates, thanks to the deployment of 10 RAI Certified Nodes.
8. **(January 2026) Improvement of final system:** Users will be able to run and test the updated system. They will be able to experiment with all RAISE features and familiarise themselves with using, reusing, and creating new validated results that will be easily stored and preserved on blockchain.

4 Analysis of the RAISE proposed timeline

Each RAISE sprint is analysed below in terms of technical advancements and per the incentives it offers the users.

4.1 Sprint 1 – June 2023

This Sprint focuses on **data upload and dataset finding**.

What can be tested by the community

In this system increment, the user will be able to login and interact with a mock-up of the dataset upload and dataset finder portal in order to have a first view of the user experience. The user will also be able to insert dataset metadata.

4.2 Sprint 2 - September 2023

This Sprint focuses on **preparing the analysis script**.

What can be tested by the community

At this stage, although a user can test a complete use-case, some core functionalities will be not yet available. Only a restricted number of datasets will be available that will be uploaded only for testing purposes. The synthetic data generator will be available only for this specific test datasets. The uploaded script will not be tested for security or quality.

The user will be able to upload a dataset and get information about the anonymization features. The user will be also able to search and find one of the existing test datasets and download the synthetic data. The processing script can then be tested on synthetic data. When the script is ready, the user will be able to upload the processing script, run in the real data and get back the results.

4.3 Sprint 3 - March 2024

This Sprint focuses on **Focus on remotely run/processing and registering experiments**.

What can be tested by the community

This increment adds on the functionalities demonstrated and tested during the previous Sprint 2. The user will be able to get some descriptive statistics of the available datasets or for the uploaded datasets that follow RAISE data models. An addition to the synthetic data generation engine will be that researchers will be able to prepare and register/upload the synthetic data asset (or an anonymized short version) of their dataset, if their dataset does not follow a supported format and

synthetic data cannot be calculated automatically. This increment will also support data and code versioning for sharing algorithms publicly.

4.4 Sprint 4 - September 2024

This Sprint focuses on **getting registered results & Publish Results & RAI Validates Authenticity of results**

What can be tested by the community

This increment will advance on the dataset upload by providing the plagiarism checker component that will be responsible to check for duplicate datasets and ensure the dataset ownership. During the upload, different dataset policies will be also foreseen as well as different openness policies for the uploaded scripts (e.g., public and private). The user will be able to find and reuse already uploaded algorithms that are open to the community. In this Sprint, the publishing of results will become also available. The system will provide the functionality of running consecutive experiments in multiple RAI nodes and the interoperability with DOI and ORCID will be also investigated.

4.5 Sprint 5 - January 2025

This Sprint focuses on popular dataset preservation.

What can be tested by the community

RAI system will offer a component that will identify the most popular datasets and make them available in RAI Central Hubs. The researchers that have uploaded popular datasets will be asked to test the interaction for popular dataset preservation. All the users will be also able to find and validate other registered results.

4.6 Sprint 6 - May 2025

This Sprint focuses on **processing script resources**.

What can be tested by the community

This Sprint focuses on enhancing the processing script resources. The new functionalities that will be added for script processing are the RAISE SDKs that will support Visual Studio Code extensions, the functionality for getting back results for code quality and code security and also working with scripts that will combine datasets from more than one node.

4.7 Sprint 7 - September 2025

This Sprint focuses on the deployment of new nodes.

What can be tested by the community

This Sprint will test the procedure of deployment of new RAI nodes. The availability of resources and system requirements for the deployment of RAI nodes will be investigated. The RAI node status updates will be also implemented during this Sprint.

4.8 Sprint 8 - January 2026

This Sprint focuses on the improvement of the final system.

What can be tested by the community

In this system increment, the user will be able to run and test the updated system. The user will be able to experiment with all RAISE features and familiarise themselves with using, reusing, and creating new validated results that will be easily stored and preserved on blockchain.